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Privatization of state tasks in the field of public security and order: a doctrinal aspect

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Abstract. Article is devoted to the doctrinal understanding of the upward social and legal trend of privatization of state tasks in the field of public security and order. Particular attention is paid to establishing the basic provisions of the theory of public tasks privatization, the characterization of certain definitions of governmental nature, the elucidation of the features of the administrative and legal nature of the subjects of delegated authority, the definition of specifics of the police administrative personality as a key subject of public administration, identification of strategic directions of individual police tasks privatization, as well as the ways of innovating domestic legislation and modernizing mechanisms detecting and eliminating threats to the protected state common good.

1 Introduction

Genesis of the state as a unique social and legal institution is objectively conditioned by the pursuit to regulate social relations, balance the interests of different social groups, ensure welfare and security, "peace, order and good governance". The state is vested with a supreme power, including the capability to intervene in the life of civil society, limit the subjective rights and freedoms of individuals, as well as with the monopoly right to apply legal coercion (institutionalized violence) in the context of fulfilling the strategic task to protect a formally defined and legislated common good. Axiomatically, the development of the state power-management infrastructure is carried out with the necessary consideration of the need to ensure the implementation of a series of inherent state functions, first and foremost, public safety and order functions. Continuous expansion of the range of threats to the state-protected goods preconditioned the introduction of privatization of certain state tasks in the field of public security and order as an innovative form of the exercise of public authority.

The problem of privatization of certain governmental state tasks in the field of public security has not been comprehensively considered in domestic jurisprudence and public administration science. Some attempts to "approach" this problem were of a sporadic and indirect nature, which makes it impossible to form a holistic objective view of the essence of this phenomenon.

The purpose of the study is to comprehend doctrinal principles of the complex social and legal phenomenon of privatization of state tasks in the field of public security and order

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in the context of the general European scientific discourse on the implementation of the provisions of the good governance doctrine and "divestiture" of certain spheres of public administration, as well as on the analysis of the "authority outsourcing" practice.

2 Results

In the latter half of the 20th century, developed democracies recognized the dichotomy of public-administrative activities, which included a classical state-administrative component based on the imperative method and a public-service component based on the dispositive method of legal regulation. The complex administrative-legal concept of "public administration" was articulated as a regulated by the legal norms of externally oriented public-power activity of authorized subjects of public administration, aimed at realization of legitimate public interest by ensuring the law and supporting legislation enforcement, facilitation of the individuals in the exercise of subjective rights, freedoms and legitimate interests, provision of administrative services, and detection, identification and neutralization of real and potential threats for the state-protected common good. Instead, the definition of "public administration entity" was derived as a system of public authorities empowered by law or an administrative contract to exercise public-authority management functions to ensure legitimate public interest. Based on the functional feature, the "catalogue of public administration entities" includes the following four elements: executive authorities; public authorities that do not belong to executive bodies, but are empowered to exercise certain governmental management functions; local self-government bodies; subjects of delegated authority (in the performance of their governmental management functions of the executive body or local self-government body).

The separation of subjects of delegated authority is a result of the long-standing debate on the ineffectiveness of excessive authority centralization, importance of establishing public-private partnerships in the governmental sphere, and the expediency of securing partial "privatization / divestiture" of authority by means of delegation of state-owned authorities to private legal entities ("authority outsourcing"). Delegation in a broad sense is interpreted as a delegation of authorities for a certain term by law or administrative contract with a retention of the delegating entity rights to control the status and consequences of their implementation and a possibility to return them to their own performance in case the contractor does not meet the formal requirements.

Privatization of public tasks is an effective means of ensuring the public sector development. Depending on the level of private legal entities involvement in the execution of public tasks, partial and general privatization are distinguished. Partial privatization concludes allowing non- governmental subjects to carry out certain public tasks while retaining the authority of state and/or municipal bodies to perform public tasks. Instead, general privatization contemplates a full delegation of powers to non-governmental subjects to perform certain public tasks. At the same time in the administrative law of some European countries the tradition of organizational privatization separation (state delegates on a temporary basis the authority to perform certain tasks to specially created private legal entities), functional privatization (state delegates on a temporary basis the authority to perform certain tasks to existing subject matter private legal entities), material privatization (state fully delegates the authority to authority to perform certain public tasks to private legal entities).

Privatization of public tasks was initiated in the 1960s in the United States in the context of finding ways to overcome the financial crisis of municipalities that traditionally perform public tasks on their own, relying solely on their own resources. In times of crisis, it has been recognized that one way to optimize budget expenses may be to involve individuals in the execution of certain public tasks, since an individual by definition acts "more economically and rationally". The concept was further developed through the efforts

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of the British Margaret Thatcher's government. In Eastern European countries limited privatization of governmental tasks began in the 1990s in the context of dismantling the archaic totalitarian government system.

The theory of privatization of public tasks is based on the following doctrinal postulates: it is unacceptable to use a private organizational legal form to exercise governmental authority, except when individuals ("special agents") are granted authority on the basis of law or an administrative contract; the use of new organizational forms should not lead to restrictions on the subjective rights and freedoms of individuals and must necessarily correlate with legitimate public interests (orders, expectations); only facilitating/supporting public tasks are subject to privatization, and the state focuses on performing strategic public tasks; the tasks performed by private legal entities shall remain unaffected and the public services rendered by them shall remain publicly available and in demand; the state continues to be responsible for the quality of the individuals public tasks performance; the state retains regulatory and supervisory powers over private legal entities that perform certain public tasks; in the performance of certain public tasks delegated by the state, private legal entities are indirectly involved in public administration and de jure belong to the subjects of public administration, and therefore their decisions, actions or omissions may be appealed in administrative court or in accordance with administrative complaint procedures. It should be noted that the privatization of public tasks inevitably results in the transformation of the legal status of authorized subjects, since there is a rotation of a public legal entity into a private legal entity that uses specific procedures/algorithms for private administration. Also note that the privatization of public tasks is fundamentally only about changing the way they are performed. It does not in any way narrow down the tasks of the state and/or municipal authorities, nor cause a change in the nature of these tasks. The decisive markers of its evaluation are efficiency of public tasks, saving of public funds, level of customer satisfaction.

The upward administrative and legal trend of privatization of public tasks is of primary importance in the field of public security and order. According to Article 3 of the Constitution of Ukraine, it is stated that "the human being, his or her life and health, honour and dignity, inviolability and security are recognised in Ukraine as the highest social value". Security in a broad sense is a state of protection of a complex social system, its stability and resistance to the influence of destructive external and internal factors. The recognition of human security as a social value and its belonging to the state-protected goods is objectively conditioned by the awareness of its existential value, necessity of for timely detection and elimination of the factors that pose a threat to humans, provision of conditions for normal life and maximum self-realization of each individual. According to Clause 3, Part 1, Article 1 of the Law of Ukraine "On National Security of Ukraine", a legitimate definition of the concept of "public security and order" is given as a protection of the interests, vital for society and individuals, rights and freedoms of man and citizen, ensuring of which is a priority activity for the security forces, other public authorities, local self-government bodies, their officials and the public, who take concerted actions to implement and protect national interests from the threats. In general, public safety should be interpreted as a state of protection of the subjective rights and freedoms, public interests and interests of individuals "against unlawful encroachments, emergencies that threaten to harm lives, health and property of a significant number of persons". The special social significance of the function of ensuring public safety and order is due to the complication of crime rate situation, absence of a balanced system of crisis management of public administration in case of emergencies and crises, inefficiency of programs for prevention of offenses and social pathologies, limited budget financing of the law enforcement bodies, shortage of highly qualified personnel, need to recruit socially active citizens to exercise law enforcement, etc.

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Basic provisions of the current European doctrine of privatization of individual state tasks in the field of public security and order are:

- the state is responsible for ensuring public safety and order, its tasks in this area are of a governmental managerial nature, only the state is vested with the monopoly right to use legal coercion/violence (right to intervene);

- the state is obliged to ensure an adequate/acceptable level of security within the available budgetary and organizational capacities. Anything beyond the "minimum security" guaranteed by the state qualifies as luxury (in the sense of "comfort and wealth-related life benefit"), which an individual orders at the security services market additionally and is paid for one's own account;

- since the state is unable to provide absolute security to a citizen as a "taxpayer and public service customer", it is obliged to take systematic measures to develop the security services market. "Purchase" of additional security services by a citizen does not burden the state budget, and therefore other taxpayers, at the expense of whom the "minimum security" is ensured;

- if the state is unable to provide individuals with protection against threats, it should not prohibit them from providing private protection ("private defense") against threats to public security and order;

- law enforcement is carried out using a wide range of legal proactive/preventive and reactive/repressive means. However, the maximum efficiency of law enforcement subjects can only be achieved through the establishment of partnerships with civil society and the involvement of non-governmental subjects in the performance of specific law enforcement tasks.

A proved way to ensure public safety and order is the "privatization of police tasks", which covers both individual aspects of internal organizational activities (eg demilitarization of individual positions by replacing them with civilians), as well as externally oriented governmental activities of the police as a key subject of public administration (delegation of authority to perform certain public tasks in the field of protecting society from real and potential threats, encroachment on security of a protected good to non-governmental subjects). The police are the bearer of the state monopoly on coercion, but they do not have a monopoly on public security and order. This approach allows the police to be exempt from certain public security tasks and to focus their staff on effective actions in socially significant strategic areas.

Theory and practice of law enforcement shows that the privatization of police tasks should be pursued in two strategic directions, namely:

- admission of private defense against the threat;
- delegation of individual state defense missions to the private sector.

In the implementation of private defense against threats, the following classical types of private security firms activities are allowed: provision of security services (protection of buildings, structures and territories); protection of strategic objects (enterprises, railways, nuclear power plants, military fields, etc.); guarding of convoys; protection of individuals; security advisory activities; an analysis of potential threats to specific sites or locations, etc. At the same time, experts emphasize the controversy over the practice of involving private subjects in the fulfillment of the following state tasks in the field of law enforcement: protection of shopping and entertainment centers (the problem of effective provision of public security and order in public places has become particularly pressing within the conditions of the existing terrorist threats insecurities); installation and maintenance of alarm and video monitoring systems (conducting indiscriminate mass surveillance is subject to peremptory compliance with the legislative requirements on protection of personal data); patrolling areas with a crime rate (the institutional inability of private security firms to provide effective patrolling in particularly dangerous locations), etc.

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The issue of delegating the state tasks in the field of defense against threat to private subjects is debatable. The imperative of the mandatory presence of reasonable grounds for delegating certain police tasks to the private sector is fundamental. Some analysts have questioned the consideration as sufficient justification for the sole pursuit of "unloading" the police, releasing it from performing uncharacteristic tasks of the classical police organization in this regard. An essential condition for the privatization of individual police tasks is to maintain police control over private security structures, since it is the state that is empowered to provide internal security, and non-governmental law enforcement subjects play a supporting role.

The problem of responsibilities separation between police and private security structures while ensuring "security perimeters" remains unresolved. Perimeter security status is vested in objects/territories protected by private security structures (security firms or internal security services). Most of these sites/territories belong to public places that are defined by the legislature as a "part (s) of any building, structure that is accessible or open to the public freely, or upon invitation, or for a fee, permanently, periodically, or from time to time". Considering the presence of private security personnel in these places, there is a ground to view them as being excluded from the responsibility of police officers. Under these conditions arises a "conflict of responsibility", which requires comprehensive legal regulation.

The concept of "privatization of the public security industry" was not approved in a unanimous vote. Opponents often emphasize the lack of adequate security training for staff in private security structures to carry out tasks within the competence of the police. Often refer to the logistical imperfection of private security firms (lack of extensive nationwide communication systems and databases, research centers, etc.). An important argument against the privatization of police tasks is the inability to establish effective public control over the activities of private law enforcement subjects. They also claim that the private security sector is of a purely commercial nature and is therefore incapable of performing the essential functions of the state police related to public service, public interest, rendering of police services. Thus, the focus is on the problem of "security for wealthy residents" who have the financial capacity to purchase security as a product type of product.

3 Conclusion

The prospect of deepening the privatization of certain state tasks in the field of public security and order consists of the following comprehensive measures to be taken:

- development and adoption of the Concept of privatization of certain tasks in the field of public security and order as a strategic document, where it is expedient to determine the list of fundamental state tasks in the field of public security and order, which cannot be delegated to non-governmental subjects;
- introduction of innovative approaches to engaging socially active citizens in the fulfillment of certain tasks in the field of public security and order (yes, there is a need for a radical revision of the Law of Ukraine "About participation of citizens in protection of public order and frontier", legitimization of the institute of voluntary police service, tried and tested in European countries, clear definition of the administrative legal personality of the security services of sports facilities and stewards responsible for ensuring public safety and order in the territory of sports facilities and its stands during the football matches, etc.);
- development and adoption of the draft law "On Municipal Police", which should enhance the institutional capacity of local self-government bodies and enhance the sense of security at the level of territorial communities;
- development and adoption of the draft law "On Private Detective Activity", which should legalize private detective activity as a civilized tool for collecting and analyzing

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information in the context of ensuring the constitutional rights and freedoms of man and citizen;

- more active use of the relevant non-governmental organizations potential in the development of strategic documents in the field of public safety and order, national, regional and local programs for the prevention of offenses and social pathologies;

- deepening public-private partnerships in the field of emergency prevention and reaction by means of transferring some of the risks related to the functioning of life support systems to the private sector, coordinating actions to protect critical infrastructure and basic natural resources, organizing security of places of mass gathering, exchanging information on physical and cyber threats, vulnerabilities, incidents, etc.

To summarize, it should be noted that the privatization of individual state tasks in the field of public security and order is a complex socio-legal problem. On the one hand, it is determined by the pursuit of releasing authorized public administration entities from performing specific tasks, to focus their attention on solving strategic problems of crime, social pathologies and emergencies prevention, and to save budgetary funds. On the other hand, partial "privatization of the security sector" is correlated with the expectations of citizens, since it contributes to the involvement of the private sector in the fulfillment of socially important tasks to protect the common good and neutralization of real and potential threats in the sphere of public security. Private law enforcement subjects do not compete with public authorities as they play a supporting role. The privatization of state tasks means the transfer solely of the right to carry out individual tasks to non-governmental subjects, not of the state tasks in the field of law and order, and certainly not the authorities to apply legal coercion, which is an exclusive prerogative of the state.

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